

Do They Capture All the Attention? Analyzing Google's AI Overviews Using Eye-Tracking and Quality Evaluation

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1. Introduction

Search engines are essential in daily life (Haider & Sundin, 2019; Lewandowski, 2023, p. 14). This is particularly true for Google, which holds a dominant position in the market (StatCounter, 2025b, 2025a; as of June 2025). Users typically focus their visual attention on the most prominent results on the search engine result page (SERP) and select those results frequently (e.g., Granka et al., 2004; Petrescu, 2014). This selection is crucial for content producers, like news organizations, that depend on web traffic for advertising revenue (Nielsen, 2019).

However, this dynamic is being disrupted by large language models (LLMs) that can generate coherent responses from processed information (Wolfram, 2023). In response, search engines such as Google and Bing are incorporating AI-generated summaries in prominent positions on their SERPs where user attention is the greatest.

As users increasingly encounter AI-generated summaries, it's vital to assess its impact on both users and content producers. Research shows that these summaries often lack verifiability (Liu et al., 2023), yet users tend to trust them despite invalid references (Li & Aral, 2025). Understanding the quality of AI-generated summaries and users' perceptions is essential, as the presence of AI responses might reduce clicks on conventional links. In a student project conducted in the summer semester of 2025, we studied these questions through eye-tracking and quality evaluation.

2. Central Research Questions

- *RQ1*: How does the visual attention people give to AI-generated summaries compare to that of other result types?
- *RQ2*: Is there a difference in visual attention between Google's and Bing's AI-generated summaries?
- *RQ3*: Do people click on the links provided in the source references of the AI-generated summaries?
- *RQ4*: What is the information quality provided in Google AI overviews?

3. Methods

We conducted two sub-studies: an eye-tracking study with survey elements and a quality evaluation of Google's AI overviews.

In a laboratory user study involving 50 participants, we had them complete 12 search tasks based on predefined Google and Bing SERPs that included AI-generated summaries. For instance, one task was "Why is the universe expanding?". We utilized eye-tracking technology to record participants' visual attention and click behavior on the SERPs (for visual attention, see Duchowski, 2007, p. 3). We examined how much attention different search results received, including AI-generated summaries, the

sources linked within those summaries, advertisements, and organic results. We also analyzed the click behavior among these varied elements. After completing these tasks, participants filled out a brief survey that included demographic information, their trust in AI, and their familiarity with AI features.

Additionally, we performed a quality evaluation of 280 Google AI overviews using a standardized questionnaire (Lee et al., 2002) to assess criteria like objectivity and believability, evaluated by the seminar students.

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References

- Duchowski, A. T. (2007). Eye Tracking Methodology: Theory and Practice. In *Eye Tracking Methodology*. Springer.
- Granka, L. A., Joachims, T., & Gay, G. (2004). Eye-tracking analysis of user behavior in WWW search. *Proceedings of the 27th Annual International Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval - SIGIR '04*, 478–479. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1008992.1009079>
- Haider, J., & Sundin, O. (2019). *Invisible Search and Online Search Engines*. Routledge.
- Lee, Y. W., Strong, D. M., Kahn, B. K., & Wang, R. Y. (2002). AIMQ: a methodology for information quality assessment. *Information & Management*, 40(2), 133–146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206\(02\)00043-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206(02)00043-5)
- Lewandowski, D. (2023). *Understanding Search Engines*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22789-9>
- Li, H., & Aral, S. (2025). *Human Trust in AI Search: A Large-Scale Experiment* (No. arXiv:2504.06435). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.06435>
- Liu, N., Zhang, T., & Liang, P. (2023). Evaluating Verifiability in Generative Search Engines. *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2023*. Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2023, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.findings-emnlp.467>
- Nielsen, R. K. (2019). Economic Contexts of Journalism. In K. Wahl-Jorgensen & T. Hanitzsch (Eds.), *The Handbook of Journalism Studies* (2nd ed., pp. 324–340). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315167497-21>
- Petrescu, P. (2014). *Google Organic Click-Through Rates in 2014*. <https://moz.com/blog/google-organic-click-through-rates-in-2014>
- StatCounter. (2025a). *Search Engine Market Share Europe | StatCounter Global Stats*. <https://gs.statcounter.com/search-engine-market-share/all/europe>
- StatCounter. (2025b). *Search Engine Market Share United States Of America | StatCounter Global Stats*. <https://gs.statcounter.com/search-engine-market-share/all/united-states-of-america>
- Wolfram, S. (2023). *What is ChatGPT doing ... And why does it work?* Wolfram Media, Inc.